

Mat Raw2023

2nd International Conference
on Raw Materials and
Circular Economy

*Raw Materials:
Setting the foundations for
the Green Transition*

28 Aug - 02 Sep
Zappeion Megaron
Athens, Greece

Book of Abstracts

Organized by

National Technical
University of Athens

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Technical Chamber
of Greece

Seabed mining and blue growth: Exploring the potential of marine mineral deposits as a sustainable source of strategic and critical raw materials
KN-02

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Minerals are major geopolitical actors in the present world. Supply chains of strategic and critical raw materials like cobalt, copper, lithium, nickel and rare earth elements are highly concentrated, generating risks. Clean energies, high- and new-technologies depend on the sourcing of several elements to Industry, and the mining activity is the core of the solution. Scarcity of critical minerals and the exhausting situation of many of the onshore mineral deposits is conducting to new developments to explore deeper, not only the Continental Crust but also on the seafloor, from coastal areas to deep sea abyssal plains.

A number of mineral deposit types, including high and low temperature hydrothermal, phosphorites, cobalt-rich ferromanganese crusts, and manganese nodules in deep-sea; and marine placers in shallow waters are covering, in a pristine conditions, the seafloor. All these deposits are particularly attractive for their polymetallic nature with high contents of strategic and critical metals.

The International Seabed Authority, the intergovernmental regulator for the exploration and future exploitation of seabed minerals beyond the national jurisdictions, is in the loop of a complex and challenging equation. Co, Ni, Mn, Te or REEs from seabed minerals, can contribute to replace oil and gas with solar panels or wind turbines looking to minimize carbon emissions. But there is a price, the pristine and not yet well understood marine environment. During the last years the technological developments on nascent deep-sea mining have been continuous but concerns over the potential environmental impacts are increasing at the same time. A precautionary principle is proposed by EU in order to protect life and health of the oceans. The international community needs to increase its knowledge on the seas before any commercial mining contract. New investments in exploration and research are mandatory, including regulations, geosphere, biosphere and hydrosphere studies.